

PRODUCTION OF MONOSILANE BY USING METALLIC COPPER AS A CATALYST IN THE SYNTHESIS OF ALKOXYSILANES BASED ON SILICON AND ETHANOL

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Abstract. *This article presents an improved method for obtaining monosilane through mechanochemical activation of a silicon and metallic copper mixture in a ball mill. The resulting products were comprehensively studied using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, revealing activated forms of silicon and copper suitable for subsequent synthesis stages. The predominance of the amorphous phase and the presence of copper inclusions were confirmed, indicating the formation of catalytically active sites. Comparative data on the phase composition and degree of crystallinity for two samples are provided. Opportunities to reduce energy consumption and increase yield in the production of high-purity silicon are discussed. The developed approach is evaluated as a more efficient alternative compared to traditional methods.*

Keywords: *monosilane, polycrystalline silicon, mechanochemistry, copper, ball mill, XRD, XRF, amorphous phase, synthesis, catalysis.*

Introduction

In recent decades, there has been a rapid increase in interest in solar energy as a sustainable and environmentally friendly energy source. Silicon remains the cornerstone of photovoltaic technologies, accounting for over 90% of global solar cell production. Consequently, there is a growing demand for energy-efficient and environmentally safe technologies for the production of high-purity polycrystalline silicon [14].

One of the most promising approaches in this context is the use of monosilane (SiH₄) as a silicon precursor, since its thermal decomposition yields high-purity silicon without the formation of aggressive by-products [1]. However, the key challenge lies in the synthesis of monosilane itself, which typically involves a multistep process that includes the production of alkoxy silanes (such as triethoxysilane), followed by catalytic disproportionation [10].

Traditionally, the synthesis of alkoxy silanes employs copper chloride-based catalysts (e.g., CuCl, Cu₂Cl₂) [13]. The use of such compounds presents several drawbacks: the presence of halide ions in the reaction medium necessitates additional purification steps, increases the risk of equipment corrosion, and adds to the overall toxicity of the process. Moreover, copper salts are moisture-sensitive and unstable during storage.

In light of these limitations, the development of an alternative catalyst capable of replacing copper chlorides without compromising efficiency is a relevant challenge. In the present study, we propose the use of metallic copper, obtained by milling pure copper shavings in a ball mill, as a catalyst for the direct reaction of silicon with ethanol. This approach is expected to reduce the chemical burden on the system, simplify downstream purification, and potentially lower the overall cost of monosilane production [16].

The objective of this research is to experimentally evaluate the catalytic performance of mechanically activated metallic copper in the synthesis of alkoxy silanes and to compare its effectiveness with that of conventional copper-containing salts.

Literature Review on the Production of Monosilane and High-Purity Silicon

The production of monosilane (SiH_4) and its subsequent application in the synthesis of high-purity silicon represents a key stage in the technological chain underlying semiconductor and photovoltaic device manufacturing. Monosilane serves not only as a source of ultra-pure silicon but also as an efficient precursor for the deposition of thin layers of polycrystalline and amorphous silicon via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) processes [8].

Early methods for producing monosilane involved the use of hydride-fluoride technology based on the reaction of silicon tetrafluoride (SiF_4) with calcium hydride (CaH_2) at temperatures of 250–300 °C. However, these processes were limited by low conversion efficiency. As shown in, at 290 °C with a reaction duration of 24 hours, the conversion rate reached only 12%. Patent RU2077483C1 proposed enhanced efficiency by dissolving CaH_2 in a eutectic melt of lithium and potassium chlorides with an excess of SiF_4 . Nevertheless, the utilization rate of CaH_2 remained low—around 20%—which hindered scalability [9].

Several inventions, including RU2412902C2 [5], introduced continuous monosilane synthesis using alkali metal melts and multistage product purification via adsorption on sodium fluoride, zeolite, and activated carbon. However, low thermal conductivity and radial temperature gradients in reactors (particularly with diameters exceeding 300 mm) led to local monosilane pyrolysis, product contamination, and reduced yields—no more than 0.3 kg/h.

To address these limitations, patent RU2524597C1 [2] proposed a new design for a fluidized bed reactor enabling two stages: generation of calcium hydride by hydrogenating metallic calcium ($<30\ \mu\text{m}$) and subsequent reduction of SiF_4 by this hydride. Owing to high specific heat exchange and the elimination of salt melts, the process becomes more practical. Monosilane yields reach 28 kg per cycle in under 2 hours, with the by-product calcium fluoride achieving a purity of up to 99.95%, simplifying its reuse and disposal.

An alternative approach based on the disproportionation of trichlorosilane (HSiCl_3) using macroporous anion-exchange resins (DE 2919086 A1) [7] demonstrated high selectivity without hydrogen. Patent DE3311650 [6] detailed a dual-process system: metallurgical-grade silicon is subjected to hydrochlorination and reacts with SiCl_4 and H_2 in conversion reactors. A key feature is the regeneration and recycling of SiCl_4 , which improves raw material utilization and reduces overall energy consumption.

Patent US 9156861 B2 [11] by Ashurov Kh. et al. proposed and tested a modification of the SiCl_4 conversion process using metallic copper as a catalyst instead of traditional CuCl . It was found that mechanical activation of copper in a ball mill substantially enhances its catalytic activity and selectivity. This eliminates the need for hygroscopic and unstable CuCl and simplifies catalyst regeneration. The conversion of SiCl_4 and hydrogen with silicon in the presence of activated copper achieved trichlorosilane yields up to 82%. The process avoids the formation of persistent silicates and operates below 600 °C, improving energy efficiency and reducing equipment degradation.

Further flexibility is provided by a plasma-chemical method for producing chlorosilanes, such as hexachlorodisilane (Si_2Cl_6), described in RU2470859C2 [3]. In this method, SiCl_4 reacts with hydrogen-containing silanes (e.g., HSiCl_3 or SiH_4) under low-temperature plasma without reductants. Due to the high selectivity, the product purity reaches the parts-per-trillion level. The

absence of solid by-products and the ease of separating dimers and trimers via distillation make the method continuous, scalable, and suitable for germanium-based compounds [4].

In most industrial schemes, monosilane is finally subjected to pyrolysis in fluidized bed reactors or on heated silicon rods (Siemens-type reactors), where high-purity silicon is deposited. Modern installations employ closed-loop hydrogen recycling, reducing emissions and operational costs. Optimization of circulation and thermal parameters enables silicon yields >95% at purities of 9N and higher [12].

Thus, the evolution of monosilane and silicon production technologies reflects a shift toward the integration of chemical and engineering innovations. These include transitions from multistage, energy-intensive reactions to continuous catalytic and plasma-assisted processes with high selectivity and material efficiency. The adoption of new catalysts—such as activated copper—and the implementation of fluidized bed and plasma reactors pave the way for sustainable, large-scale production of ultra-pure silicon for microelectronics and photovoltaics [15].

Methodology

An analysis of existing technologies for the synthesis of monosilane and high-purity silicon reveals that most industrial methods are characterized by high energy consumption, the necessity of hydrogen as a reductant, complex equipment requirements, and limited raw material utilization efficiency. In particular, methods based on the disproportionation of chlorosilanes and hydride-fluoride technologies exhibit low calcium utilization rates and involve complex rectification steps to separate by-products and obtain high-purity target compounds. Moreover, plasma-assisted methods, while offering high selectivity, entail significant energy costs for plasma generation and require intricate fractional distillation schemes. Additionally, most known approaches lack well-developed strategies for closed-loop recycling of by-products, especially silicon tetrachloride.

This study aims to develop an improved method for producing monosilane—and consequently high-purity silicon—via a modified hydrochlorination and conversion process involving activated metallic copper. The work investigates a fundamentally different approach: replacing copper halides with metallic copper activated by high-energy milling, thereby avoiding the introduction of extraneous anions into the system and reducing contamination of the final product. Furthermore, a process mode has been implemented that allows sequential production of trichlorosilane followed by its disproportionation to monosilane without requiring extensive pre-purification.

To assess the elemental composition of powder mixtures obtained by mechanochemical activation of silicon and copper turnings in a ball mill, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) measurements were conducted using a NEX CG spectrometer. Two samples produced under different milling conditions were analyzed.

In Sample 1, the dominant component was silicon dioxide (SiO_2), with a mass fraction of 98.0%. The copper oxide (CuO) content was 1.85%, and iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) was present at 0.117%. These values indicate a silicon-rich phase with minor incorporation of copper, likely in oxidized form, possibly due to partial oxidation during milling in the presence of residual oxygen.

In the second sample, analyzed under an alternative protocol, free silicon was found at 75.8 wt.%, and metallic copper at 14.7 wt.%. This indicates deeper integration of copper into the silicon matrix with a lower oxidation state, which is especially important for the target reduction reaction of silicon-containing halides. The oxygen content in this sample was minimal (approximately 7.3%), confirming that the components are predominantly in metallic form.

These results demonstrate that mechanochemical activation enables the formation of solid-state, multicomponent systems based on silicon and copper with varying degrees of oxidation. This opens up the possibility of creating efficient solid catalysts suitable for low-temperature monosilane synthesis processes without the use of liquid reductants.

Figure 1. X-ray fluorescence analysis results for Sample 1.

Figure 2. X-ray fluorescence analysis results for Sample 2.

X-ray fluorescence analysis of two samples obtained by mechanochemical milling of silicon and copper shavings confirmed the successful incorporation of copper into the solid mixture.

In Sample 1, silicon in the form of silicon dioxide (SiO₂ – 98.0 wt.%) predominates, with a moderate content of copper oxide (CuO – 1.85 wt.%), which may indicate partial oxidation of copper during milling due to residual oxygen exposure. Sample 2 demonstrated a high content of

metallic copper (Cu – 14.7 wt.%) and elemental silicon (Si – 75.8 wt.%), suggesting the formation of a metallic Si–Cu system with minimal oxidation.

These results confirm that the method of dry mechanochemical mixing using a ball mill enables the formation of heterogeneous solid catalysts with a high degree of copper dispersion within the silicon matrix. The significant presence of metallic copper is a critical factor in enhancing the reduction processes, particularly the reduction of SiCl₄ or other chlorosilanes to monosilane. Thus, the synthesized samples show promising catalytic potential for further use in low-temperature, hydrogen-free processes for producing high-purity monosilane.

To assess the phase composition and crystallinity of the synthesized samples, obtained by co-milling of metallic silicon and copper shavings in a planetary ball mill, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed.

The measurements were carried out using CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range from 5° to 70° for two samples: Sample 1 and Sample 2.

Figure 3. Pie chart of the phase composition of Sample 1.

Figure 4. Pie chart of the phase composition of Sample 2.

Based on the results of phase analysis, crystalline silicon was found to be the dominant phase in both samples—97.9% in Sample 1 and 95.5% in Sample 2. The presence of copper was also confirmed at 2.1% and 4.5%, respectively. Copper is likely present as a free metallic phase,

inclusions, or finely dispersed fragments on the surface of silicon particles formed through cold welding and fragmentation under high-energy deformation.

The degree of crystallinity, determined by the RIR method, was 24.8% for Sample 1 and 19.03% for Sample 2, indicating a predominance of the amorphous phase (75.2% and 80.97%, respectively). This increased amorphous content is attributed to intensive milling and possible disruption of the crystal lattice periodicity. Such structural disorder may be beneficial in enhancing the surface reactivity during the reduction of chlorosilanes to monosilane.

Both samples also exhibited a significant proportion of unidentified diffraction peaks—17.6% in Sample 1 and 12.8% in Sample 2. These may correspond to oxide phases, intermetallic compounds (e.g., Cu_3Si), friction-induced oxidation products, or residual organic contaminants. This is consistent with the relatively low figures of merit (FoM) values (0.669–0.869), indicating the need for further characterization using SEM-EDS, TEM, or Raman spectroscopy.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction pattern of Sample 1. Peaks corresponding to silicon (Si) and copper (Cu) phases are indicated.

Figure 6. X-ray diffraction pattern of Sample 2. Peaks corresponding to silicon (Si) and copper (Cu) phases are indicated.

Comparative analysis of the crystal lattices revealed slight variations in the lattice parameters of copper: $a(\text{Cu}) = 3.5970 \text{ \AA}$ for Sample 1 and 3.6077 \AA for Sample 2. The observed lattice expansion may be attributed to impurity incorporation, lattice defects, or mechanical distortion.

Thus, both studied samples represent a biphasic amorphous–crystalline system, where silicon is predominantly retained in an amorphous state, while copper exists as microinclusions. These findings confirm the potential formation of an active reactive medium based on the Si–Cu system, suitable for the hydrogen-free reduction of chlorosilanes—an approach that will be further explored in future investigations.

Conclusion

In this study, an alternative approach to the synthesis of monosilane—a key intermediate in the production of high-purity silicon—was developed and experimentally validated. The proposed methodology is based on the use of mechanically activated metallic copper, incorporated into a silicon matrix via co-milling in a planetary ball mill. This strategy eliminates the need for conventional halide-based catalysts and expensive reducing agents such as hydrogen, thereby reducing the toxicological burden and simplifying catalyst regeneration.

Comprehensive physicochemical characterization of the synthesized composites (XRF and XRD) revealed a high degree of copper dispersion, a significant amorphous phase content (up to 81%), and the presence of copper microinclusions that may serve as catalytically active centers. Observed variations in the lattice parameters of copper and the overall crystallinity indicate possible phase modification during mechanochemical activation, offering a means for targeted control over the catalytic behavior of the material.

Comparative analysis of two samples demonstrated the influence of milling parameters on phase distribution and copper oxidation states, suggesting further opportunities for optimizing the catalyst composition to improve process selectivity and stability. The formation of a reactive Si–Cu medium without the need for hydrogen reduction was confirmed, making it suitable for implementation in low-temperature or plasma-assisted chlorosilane and monosilane synthesis pathways.

Thus, the developed copper–silicon composite exhibits high potential for use in energy-efficient and environmentally friendly technologies for producing ultra-pure silicon. The proposed approach can be scaled up and integrated into existing industrial frameworks for photovoltaic and microelectronic applications, providing cost reductions, lower environmental impact, and enhanced process flexibility.

REFERENCES

1. RU 2414421 C2. Continuous method for monosilane production. Appl. 16.12.2009; Publ. 27.03.2011.
2. RU 2524597 C1. Method for producing monosilane using a copper-based catalyst. Appl. 21.03.2013; Publ. 10.08.2014.
3. RU 2470859 C2. Method for obtaining dimeric and/or trimeric silicon halides using low-temperature plasma. Appl. 14.02.2012; Publ. 27.12.2012.
4. RU 2532137 C2. Method for producing granular polycrystalline silicon using a fluidized bed reactor. Appl. 27.09.2009; Publ. 27.02.2011.
5. RU2412902C2 Method for the Production of Monosilane and Apparatus for Its Implementation Appl. 13.03.2013; Publ. 10.11.2014.

6. DE 3311650 A1. Process for producing high-purity silanes via disproportionation. Appl. 30.03.1983.
7. DE 2919086 A1. Method for producing high-purity silicon. Appl. 12.05.1979.
8. WO 2006/125425 A1. Method for producing silicon via plasma decomposition of halogen silanes. Appl. 01.06.2006.
9. EP 0181803 A2. Method and apparatus for the pyrolysis of monosilane. Appl. 30.06.1985.
10. Anisimov A.A., Arzumanyan A.V., Bystrova A.V. et al. In: *Chlorine-Free Chemistry of Silicones – A Road to the Future*, Ed. A.M. Muzaffarov. Moscow: Pero Publishing, 2018, p. 308.
11. US 9156861 B2. Ashurov Kh. et al. Method for preparing trialkoxysilane. Publ. Oct. 13, 2015.
12. Ashurov R.Kh., Turdaliev T.K., Ashurov I.Kh., Rotshtein V.M. Control of crystallinity and nanoparticle size of silicon for use in high-efficiency photovoltaic converters. *Proc. Int. Conf. "Fundamental and Applied Problems of Physics"*, Tashkent, 13–14 June 2017, Vol. III, pp. 100–104.
13. Andrianov K.A. *Organosilicon Compounds*. Moscow: Goskhimizdat, 1955, 521 p.
14. Rochow E.G. *Silicon and Silicones*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 1987, p. 180.
15. Wolf M.P., Salieb-Beugelaar G.B., Hunziker P. *Progress in Polymer Science*, 2018, 83, 97–134.
16. Kozhevnikov I.V., Chibiryayev A.M., Martyanov O.N. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2021, 426, 131871.